

FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN YOUNG PEOPLE - AS A PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7666003>

Abstract. *The article provides a theoretical analysis of the concepts of competence, social responsibility, psychological characteristics of adolescence, forms and methods of development of their social responsibility, pedagogical and psychological conditions for the formation of social competence of students and guidelines for development.*

Keywords: *social competence, adolescence, high school students, forms and methods of measuring social competence, methodology, model of a high school student, age and mental characteristics, stimulation of educational activity, creating a state of success, self-awareness, self-esteem.*

The current state of society is so multifaceted and ambiguous that it requires high skills and abilities from the individual, without which a person cannot live in society. In this regard, the problem of interpersonal communication and building a trajectory of coexistence in the social space is relevant. The success of an individual directly depends on his/her awareness of social problems, the ability to see the problem and solve it. Therefore, the main aspect of an individual's success is the formation and level of representation of social competence, which allows achieving the desired goals and getting the desired result.

In accordance with paragraph 4 of the Presidential Decree No. PD-4884 of November 6, 2020 "On additional measures for further improvement of the education system" the task "to ensure continuity of educational programs and disciplines of preschool, secondary general, vocational and higher education" is defined. The implementation of this decree also provides for the discipline "Upbringing" introduced in schools in the current school year.

In the process of modernization of modern education in the Republic of Uzbekistan one of the leading tasks is the task of formation of social competence of an individual in the process of his subjective self-consciousness in the environment in which he is brought up. The need to address this issue is determined by the mission entrusted to educational institutions by official bodies and the expectations of society, which, in turn, determines the need of citizens to develop social competence in the process of education.

If we consider social competence as the improvement of the individual in the social space, in particular, the upbringing environment of the educational institution, modeling the social behavior of a person, allows him to gain experience of subjective self-awareness, to develop social abilities. It is this position that becomes important in the process of social competence formation through the upbringing environment. As a result of the process of students' socialization, i.e. as a result of real interaction between the school and the environment, their social competences of a new level emerge. Then the formation of social competence, today, will be one of the most important pedagogical tasks for the modern school.

Adolescence in general education schools falls in grades 10-11. The majority of sociologists define belonging to youth as age from 16 to 29 years old. S.I. Ikonnikova and T.S. Lisovskaya, analyzing the age aspect of the young generation, emphasize that not only age, but also the importance of the similarity of their views, attitudes and goals for life is of special significance in this case. The young generation will not lose their social character in the social space in which they live. The commonality of young people's views, interests, values, actions and desires is the main indicator of their emerging life position in relation to society. As V. Chuprova notes, "...a special socially significant aspect of youth is determined by the inheritance ... system of social relations of representatives of the young generation... and ability to adapt it to life by recycling it".

The scientist-psychologist E. Gaziev notes that "in early adolescence students feel the need for conscious, systematic, orderly, consistent and systematic formation of the most valuable qualities, learning skills in themselves. As we know, students in this category of educational institutions are looking for a reasonable dimension, a criterion, a perfect, ideal image, performing tasks, a role model, an image of high dreams, to have a spiritual and psychological image." Therefore, any activity conducted with students during this period will have an effective impact.

Young people are currently defined as people who have reached the age of 14 and under the age of 30 in accordance with the current normative act of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and perspective citizens seeking to pursue their interests, that is, the socially active part of the population. Therefore, this social group is characterized by such features as physical maturation, formation as an individual, entering into legal relations in the main spheres of society (economy, law, politics and family relations).

The youth group (high school students), which we identified as the object of our study, is a social group with a specific character in need of attention. As it is known, nowadays high school students of comprehensive schools are adolescents under the age of 16-17 years old. This social group of young people is called *adolescent youth* by specialists. In the encyclopedia of upbringing: adolescence - a period of human development from about 15 to 18 years, in pedagogy it is also called "high school age". At the end of adolescence, boys and girls usually reach puberty both physically and mentally.

The problem of developing social competence in an individual during adolescence can seem extremely relevant, as evidenced by numerous studies recently conducted in Uzbekistan and beyond its borders. The absolute complexity of this problem and its importance for practice have prompted the writing of many works directly related to the consideration of the formation of social competence. At the same time, the currently available methods of increasing social competence (lectures, training sessions, printed materials, various educational and outreach programs, etc.) do not always sufficiently take into account the interests and inclinations of adolescents, especially their age. In addition, they do not always reflect the complexity of the situation in modern society. Often they are divided into parts that are primarily aimed at the development of certain aspects of social competence, are not generally accessible and require considerable time and money to implement.

Microfactors that influence a student include family, peers, microcommunity, and various educational and upbringing organizations. The school should actively participate in the process of socialization of secondary school students, interact with microfactors from the list, take into account their direct influence on the formation of the student's personality. School as an

educational institution carries out the formation of the social order - a personality that meets the requirements of a particular society, era, educating and upbringing of the younger generation with maximum consideration of the social conditions of their residence and work.

Hence one of the goals facing the educational institution today: to create the necessary conditions for the formation of high-level social competence, the choice of methods and techniques of pedagogy, social psychology. Such conditions can be created by using the possibilities of the educational environment of the educational institution, directing all attention not to the children, but to their environment, the environment of life in which children interact.

Under such conditions, the school must be reorganized organizationally, substantively, and technologically, taking into account the requirements for graduates. The main task of education is to educate a student capable of entering society on the basis of elements of culture, social norms and values learned at school.

Based on these goals and objectives, we can talk about the final result of learning in a modern school, i.e. the competence of a graduate.

The Council of Europe has identified five main groups of competencies that, according to UNESCO, should be possessed by secondary school graduates. The first group includes social responsibilities, mastering which allows school graduates to take responsibility, actively participate in developing joint solutions, positively resolve conflict situations, and effectively participate in the activities of various democratic institutions.

After the 1990s, social competence becomes a requirement in all social spheres of human life as an individual, is seen as an interdisciplinary subject and is analyzed as a complex, multicomponent and multidimensional phenomenon. This trend will continue in the research of the present scholars.

In this case, V.N. Kunitsina singles out the following types of social competence: verbal competence; communicative competence; socio-professional competence; socio-psychological competence; self-identification (ego-competence).

I.A. Zimnyaya refers human and social sphere competences related to social influence to the competences of social interactions (society, collective, family, friends, partners, conflicts and their prevention, cooperation, tolerance, social mobility) (oral, written, dialogue, monologue; knowledge and observance of traditions, etiquette rules; intercultural and foreign language communication; business correspondence; communication functions).

Much attention is paid to the study of social competence by foreign authors. For example, German psychologists W. Pflingsten and R. Hintch interpret social competence as the mastery of cognitive, emotional and motor behavior that leads to a long-term positive correlation of positive and negative consequences in certain situations. According to X. Schroeder and M. Forwerg, social competence includes four personality characteristics: communicative ability, persistence, sensitivity, and self-esteem.

Thus, the analysis of existing approaches to the definition of “social competence” gives grounds to define social competence as an integrative quality of the individual, which includes the necessary knowledge, experience, abilities resulting from socialization and allowing a person to adapt sufficiently and interact effectively in the society. Social competence allows to quite solve problems in the social environment.

The conducted analyses allow us to conclude that there are different approaches in understanding the essence of social competence: social competence is presented either as an

integral quality of a personality or as a social interaction; social competence is characterized as a result of some activity or an indicator of a person's achievement of a certain type of activity; the content component of social competence formation depends on the age of a person. The process of formation and development of social competence at different ages has both general and specific features, including different and similar components.

On the basis of theoretical studies it is possible to form the following concept of social competence: a complex of knowledge about social reality, social skills, a system of social and personal qualities. The level of their formation in each person allows to form their character taking into account the peculiarities and social role of the social situation.

In our opinion, social competence is not a body of knowledge, but a person's ability to find a way out, using the skills to solve life problems and tasks, the ability to find solutions in everyday real situations, educational and life experience, social values and personal motives.

The development of social competence requires a clear definition of the age specifics of its bearers. The most difficult and important period in terms of personality development is adolescence. The general growth of a teenager's personality, the expansion of his or her range of interests, the development of self-awareness, and new experiences with peers all lead to an intense growth of social motives, values, and experiences, such as the ability to empathize with another's grief, the capacity for self-sacrifice, etc.

The development of social competence of adolescents in the educational process is successful if: the essential features of social competence as an integral personal formation are revealed: the concept is revealed, the elements of its composition and content are defined; the pedagogical tasks of the development of social competence of students on the basis of new forms, conditioned by age development and the specifics of the leading socially significant activity are highlighted; learning activities carried out by the model group of development of social competence of students in the educational process, designed and purposefully implemented through dialogic learning, discussions, debates, communicative educational technologies; development of practical problem solving skills, choice situations are implemented through organization of project activities, solving selection problem; instilling spiritual and moral values in extracurricular activities carried out through essay competitions, projects and other types of extracurricular activities. One of the most important components of a person's social competence in a complex, unstable social environment is the ability to reflect social situations.

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